

Notes

Formation Constants and I.R. Spectrum of Indium(III)-Lactate

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POTENTIOMETRIC study showed the formation of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes between In(III) and Lactic acid. The formation constants of these complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method. Approximate values of the formation constants were obtained from half-integral values and their refinement was made by the method of least-squares as well as by point-wise calculations. The I.R. spectrum of the isolated complex (1 : 3) suggests that the chelation has taken place involving co-ordination of both, hydroxyl and carboxyl, groups of the lactate ion.

Danilo Cozri and Giorgio Raspi¹ during polarographic behaviour of In(III) in presence of various organic acids observed the formation of 1 : 3 complex between In(III) and lactic acid. In view of lack of detailed information of In(III)-lactate complexes, it was considered worthwhile to undertake a physico-chemical investigation of this system in aqueous solution. The present study deals with the same.

Experimental

The stock solution of the ligand was prepared using lactic acid (B.D.H. 'Analar'). The metal solution was prepared from 99.9% pure indium(III)-nitrate pentahydrate and indium content was estimated as 8-hydroxy-quinolate². The stock solution of sodium perchlorate, to maintain constant ionic strength and perchloric acid to lower the pH to ≈ 2.0 was prepared by dissolving $\text{NaClO}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ (Riedel) and HClO_4 (E. Merck) respectively.

All other chemicals used were either B.D.H. 'Analar' or equivalent quality.

A pH-meter (Polymetron CL-41) with a combined electrode and accuracy ± 0.05 pH unit was used to determine the change in hydrogen-ion-concentration of the solution.

Conductance measurements were made using 'Philips' conductivity bridge employing a 'dip-type' conductivity cell capable of operating with 14.0 ml solution.

I.R. spectra were obtained with the help of 'Perkin Elmer Infrared-Spectrophotometer-237' using KBr disc technique.

Each solution, after its preparation, was allowed to stand for one hour in a thermostat at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$, to reach thermal equilibrium before measurements were made.

Results and Discussion

The interaction of In(III) ions with lactic acid has caused considerable lowering of pH and pH-metric titration of 1 : 1 metal-ligand system with alkali has revealed an inflection at one equivalent of alkali indicating that only carboxylic protons of the ligand are liberated consequent to chelate formation. The chelation reaction may be represented as :

pH-metric titration of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixtures of In(III) and lactic acid with alkali show inflections at two and three equivalents of alkali respectively corresponding to the formation of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes as represented by the following equations :

The inflections at two and three equivalents of alkali for 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 metal-ligand pH-metric titration indicates the absence of any poly-nuclear species which may persist in solution.

The formation of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes has been further confirmed by conductometric study employing monovariation method³ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Indium(III)-Lactate Monovariation Method

The formation constants of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (In : Lactate), complexes were determined by Bjerrum's method⁴. The aqueous solutions containing perchloric acid + ligand and perchloric acid + ligand + metal salt solution of constant volume

(50.0 ml) and constant ionic strength (0.1M NaClO₄) were titrated against standard alkali at a temperature 30°±0.1°. The pK_a value of the ligand, 3.85, as reported by Khadikar⁵ under the same experimental conditions was used for the calculation of formation constant of In(III)-lactate complexes.

In calculating $\bar{n}$ and $p^{[4-1]}$ the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values for $\bar{n}$ and $p^{[4-1]}$ corresponding to different values of pH were calculated and formation curve obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ values against $p^{[4-1]}$ (Fig. 2). From the formation curve the approximate values of log K₁, log K₂ and log K₃ were obtained from half-integral values of $\bar{n}$ and their refinement was made by the method of least squares as well as by point-wise calculations (Table 1). The standard deviation of the values of log K₁, log K₂ and log K₃ are found to be ±0.03, ±0.03 and ±0.05 respectively.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF IN(III)-LACTATES

	Bjerrum's method	Point-wise calculation	Least square method
Log K ₁	2.60	2.58	2.62
Log K ₂	1.44	1.47	1.45
Log K ₃	0.72	0.72	0.76
log β ₂	4.04	4.05	4.07
log β ₃	4.76	4.77	4.83

The 1:3 complex was isolated as described by Khadikar *et al.*⁶. The I.R. spectrum of the 1:3 complex having the composition InL₃.3H₂O (In Obs. 26.40%, Cal. 26.34%) and that of lactic acid was

Fig. 2. Formation Curve In(III)-Lactate.

obtained by KBr disc technique. Based on the bidentate nature of the ligand octahedral stereochemistry may be assigned to the complex. It seems, therefore, that the water molecules present in the complex are not co-ordinated and are in the second co-ordination sphere. Considerable shift in the hydroxyl group frequency from 3500 cm⁻¹ in lactic acid to 3300 cm⁻¹ in the complex was observed. The ionised carboxyl group stretching frequency is also found to have been shifted to 1590 cm⁻¹ (ligand 1750 cm⁻¹). This suggests that the chelation has taken place involving co-ordination of both carboxyl and hydroxyl groups of the lactate ion. The presence of water molecules could not be confirmed by the I.R. spectrum of the complex since medium absorption bands of γ(OH) in the range 3480-3400 cm⁻¹ and of δ(HOH) in the range 1640-1630 cm⁻¹ overlaps with the hydroxyl and carboxyl group frequencies of In(III)-lactate. However, a weak band at 765 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to the presence of water in the complex in accordance with Nakamoto⁷.

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References

1. D. COZRI and G. RASPI, *Ricer. Sci.*, 1957, **27**, 2392.
2. L. ERDEY, "Gravimetric Analysis", Part II, Pergamon Press, N.Y., 1965.
3. M. R. NAYER and C. S. PANDEY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.* 1948, **27A**, 284.
4. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase, Copenhagen, 1941.
5. P. V. KHADIKAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Vik. Univ., 1967.
6. P. V. KHADIKAR and R. L. AMERIA, *Science and Culture*, 1971, **37**, 306.
7. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Co-ordinated Compounds", Wiley, N.Y., 1970.

Molecular Adducts of Diaryltin dihalides with Formamide and its Substituted Derivatives

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IN continuation to our studies on the acceptor property of diaryltin dihalides¹⁻⁶, we now describe synthesis and characterisation of some new molecular adducts of diaryltin dihalides with formamide (F) and its substituted derivatives viz., N-methyl formamide (NMF), diethyl formamide (DEF) and

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